

- [MESS0027: MIMS 2.62 - the Four Domains to Win WW3.0 and WWIII](#)
- [The Once and Future American](#)

MESS 0037

MIMS 2.801 - The Eight Domain Array (8DA) of the Modern Art of War¹

Sf. R. Careaga, BSEE, MSTOM

January 2023

ABSTRACT

In this paper the author extracts highly esoteric metaphysical constructs within the martial sphere. The primary concern of the author is in the [mis]understanding of power, particularly Divine Power, which in EPEMC is taken to be a form of the Unified [Aether] Force-field, and motion of the sea of charge, and its mutual confluences. The author covers esoteric, lost topics of the previous seven domains of SEAL and the four domains, and then proceeds to discuss the literal and esoterica of the Language domain. The combination of SEAL and COTEL, leads to a more complete seal; and the use of the 7-sided shape, to replace the pentagon, which is able to handle the five present domains, but not to master the others.

Keywords: Art of War - Domain - Array - Aether - Cyberspace - Space - Economics - Technology - Language

¹ This document best viewed at: <https://bit.ly/3XLaLY6>

Note from the Author	2
Introduction	3
The Fine Science of the Art of War	3
Sea, Air, and Land - the Tripartite War Field (TWF)	4
C.O.T.E.L. - The domains of special forces/operators.	5
Cyberspace	6
Outer Space	7
Technology	8
Economics	9
The Divine Power in the Four & Five Domains	10
Cyberspatial Power	11
Outer Space Power	12
Technological Total Supremacy	13
Economic Royal Sway	13
Language as a “breaker box” for the WFCC, particularly the Internet	14
Language as a domain, via the L power; control of the P power via words.	15
Conclusion	16
References	19
Appendix	22
“The Twelve-sided Jade Knob inscription	22
The Inscription	22
The Dynamism of Heaven	22

Note from the Author

This is an extremely esoteric treatise on an old topic, brought to modern issues. The topics covered, therefore and unfortunately, require a depth of study not only within the Art of War and EPEMC Strategy Series, but the MIMS philosophy itself (f. 2021). This philosophy is rooted in leveraging future scientific knowledge and technology in the present, through understanding the facets of our scientific history which created massive advancement and rapid change.

The author is a patriot, and makes no apologies for supporting the strength of a nascent Innate Shi of the United States of America; but he is not a supporter of the Deep State, Military Industrial Complex, or New World Order(s), such as they are. He believes in empowering The People, and limiting the power of the government. However, the strategic adversaries of western civilization do not make such distinctions, and they are not pacifists. Therefore, the author releases this document to urge the Pentagon to take action, but also as a free and fair opportunity to all the world - anyone who would listen - that if they approach the Reality curve closer, through model or martiality, that they can attain the stronger Keen. If none do, then this paper is a mere exercise only, and can be disregarded, except by those interested in the particular 2.80X branch of the philosophy. In the end, pragmatism is preferred over the esoteric mimsicality contained within this. But, unlike the virtual philosophical particle the Realion, bear in mind the bingfa methods have real life consequences.

Introduction

The typical issues of the Art of War, regarding “Conventional” warfare in SEAL domains, which are still touted as the main areas of warfare development and responses, are well covered in many areas. The next four domains were covered in the previous MESSy, as is cited at the top of the title page. The final Domain, which has not been thoroughly elucidated, is covered in the eighth domain: Language. This paper will be divided into three sections. The first, a cover of finer points which do not appear to be on the radar of anyone (that the author can see) regarding nuances of the Art of War in the first 7 domains. The second section will elucidate abstractified and leverageable points of the four domains in the last paper. The final section, and greater part, is the knowledge of the eighth domain, Language, in ways that are not well understood in the West. Not to mention, a small section discussion of the potential mimsical² power (*P* power³, or ‘magickal’⁴, etc.) from having code/command control via the plasmaglyphs⁵.

The Fine Science of the Art of War

There has been much balleyhooed about the *art* of the art of war, the slippery aspect of the real grasp of the Shi⁶, which leads the deft, and perspicacious/wise general making genius moves in the field. But, while everyone knows that the quarterbacks who have grand vision and a penchant for good choices win the adulations... the consistent, scientific ones making the high percentage passes and running at the right time, and only deviating from plans as need arises are the ones that win over, and over again. So there is an *Operations Research*⁷ side of bingfa, which can be influenced by the “beancounters” and their Data Analytics. They can find “minimum critical viable paths” and “Gamify”⁸ the algorithms of war, as well as involve themselves in the wise decisions. However, what underlies all of it is a firm grasp of the “Total Shi”⁹:

- ★ Innate Shi¹⁰ (both position and resources, and present momentum, as well as generally good/positive vs. bad/negative qualities).
- ★ Positional Shi (as it lives, breathes, and moves in the moment, and is evolving)
- ★ Fluid Shi
 - FLEXION - flexible tension Yang
 - FLEND - fluid-bending Yin
 - FLENTION - fluid tension Yang+Yin
 - The ‘voltage’ potential of moving superfluid chemistry?

The finer aspect of this last is æthereal, dæthereal, and *potentially* divine. It is definitely going to be influenced by:

- *L, G, A*, domains of power and the *k* and *l* regions, particularly L.U.C.K.¹¹

² <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc/mims>

³ [MIMS 1.0 and Double Layer Economics](#)

⁴ [MIMS: The threefold Sacred Sciences](#)

⁵ [Plasma Petroglyphs \(Plasmaglyphs\), Earthworks, and the Megafauna Extinction](#)

⁶ [MIMS & Shi](#)

⁷ [MESS0007: The ORDA Standard](#)

⁸ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0747563221002867>

⁹ [MIMS: Strategy and Dualism](#)

¹⁰ [Innate Shi of Countries and US](#)

¹¹ [MIMS - The Big G of 5 Forces](#)

- *d* region, as it relates to the so-called ‘manifest destiny’, meaning what is *expected* by the collective consciousness.
- The Law of Causality¹²

** The triple overlap of this law with the *L* power and the *k* domain, only emphasizes the importance of the final section of this analysis.¹³

Sea, Air, and Land - the Tripartite War Field (TWF)

The first areas that have much left to “squeeze” out are the SEAL domains. Why are these, despite 30 years of dusty warfare and 60 years of jungle warfare, still so juicy? Primarily because the division of them into, respectively, Navy, Air Force, and Army is so cliché and typical that we have never gotten over its simplicity¹⁴. But in actuality, of course the US Military, among all and first in history, has most thoroughly and completely blended them. However, the blend is full of redundancies, a few unscientific assumptions (and let’s face it, budgeting obsessions), and bolstered by massive spending which could be more efficient and get more out of “the vine¹⁵.”

This issue of having a defacto blended force system, increasingly because of JSOC, SOCOM, and MARSOC field operations, and a philosophical division is going to create a seesaw effect, and a confusion of the Mission. Mission creep is inevitable in this. But it doesn’t have to be the end.

Rather, if the entire military is moved up to a Navy SEAL/Devgru + SSOF type vision of how military is to be, in the three basic domains, then the entire US Military now enters a whole new level of self-expectation. In fact, the National Guard becomes set to Army standards, the Coast Guard to Navy standards, and the three main branches to specop standards; rather than what we currently have: declining standards¹⁶, and decreasing behavioral standards¹⁷ in the special fighting branches vis-a-vis crime¹⁸.

¹² [MIMS 4.31-4.36- The Storage of Karma and Junk DNA](#)

¹³ [MIMS 2.21 - The Union of 5 and 8](#)

¹⁴ In the earliest days, the Vimanas of the sky - meteors and comets - led to over a thousand years of chariot driven warfare.

¹⁵ Picture the entire CENTCOM as a vine, and the entire military and intelligence communities, even paramilitary police and national guards as part of a vineyard. Seen as such offices, division, platoons, soldiers, outfits, etc. are all merely grapes to be used in the making of various wines and there are even fine vintages. Assets (while aging, not always so fine) could be put “on shelf”, and in some cases ‘unpacked’ and the ‘cork’ unsealed, taken out, and used again. But this doesn’t seem the present gardener’s obsession. It seems rather always about the Technology Domain, and spend, spend spend. Spending the American People get; but can the Pentagon and CIA not spend in a way that is both wise and respectful of the physics of the economic domain? When the economic domain is not even well understood, and the obsession is only with the 0th Domain, isn’t it likely to create a Soviet like collapse? Why even risk it? If you can “compress” your spending on most items and get the same results, and then you have the other X% of the budget, aren’t you therefore able to find the areas you failed to stand up properly before? These types of inefficiencies we will say is what happens when the gardener is besotted with the wine, and the field hands are busy eating the grapes and singing a merry song about the vineyard. But the reality is that the vineyard needs infrastructure improvements, and less incestuous bidding opportunities, to make it a strong vineyard, again.

¹⁶

<https://www.military.com/daily-news/2022/09/28/new-pentagon-study-shows-77-of-young-americans-are-ineligible-military-service.html>

¹⁷

<https://www.armytimes.com/news/your-army/2019/03/13/spec-ops-in-trouble-mired-in-scandal-and-under-pentagon-review-what-will-it-take-to-clean-house/>

¹⁸

<https://www.military.com/daily-news/2021/04/12/after-war-zone-scandals-special-operators-are-curbing-deployments-and-investing-ethics-training.html>

Worse, the “wokeification” and focus in Air Force¹⁹ and Navy²⁰ on issues that are **completely unrelated to fighting and maintaining a discriminationless fighting and defense force** has accelerated, leaving us both vulnerable, and frankly: stupid. Woke = broke, and a bankrupt military means a vulnerable home country and collective team. Cultural Marxism is a foreign [ie- Germanic] pathogen and tool of the Enemy Combatants and revolutionaries attempting or desirous to overthrow the United States of America (c.1776), for which it stands. It has no place in the military.²¹

The solution set for this - as always in Chinese sciences, and that includes bingfa (Art of War) - is Tao.

- Teamwork
 - Focus on the 3 domains as a tripartite field in every branch; CENTCOM is great at this already!
- Orientation
 - Orientate the new recruits and old soldiers - the entire Vine - along the lines of thinking in an Eighth Domain array, forcing rapidly evolutionary acceptance of the Tripartite Field, of the four domains, and of course Language²².
- Accession²³
 - Giving, controlling, taking accession, and going “up” in power levels is a matter of physics and metaphysics that has not been taught, perhaps anywhere; and this is outside the purvey of this paper. Needless to say the author will need to discuss this topic at length. Inside the Resilient Way - American Institute²⁴ there are internal documents that define the issue; but at present, this particular topic of “up-leveling” has not been elucidated. Nevertheless, the US Military has found ways to “level up” through combat training and calculated risk, and perhaps over-strain of the forces, and now at present is dealing with the fatigue of this. The PTSD of it is not well understood.

C.O.T.E.L. - The domains of special forces/operators.

Achieving the TAO of the bingfa in a modern Art of War is simply not possible without the CO(S)TEL approach.

We have to grasp the “operative function” of the use of the COTEL mentality. It is to produce an iterative, operative five-domain and/or subdomain array that has the same superfluidity as the tripartite SEAL field. Yet it enables more capabilities (with scaled organization) and acts together with it to maintain the cohesion of the “Big G” fibonacci code; $5+3=8$.²⁵

Think about this; the eight laws are practically sacrosanct in the religious **and** scientific spheres of influence, why? Because they are mimsical expressions of real *P* power aspects of the G.O.D. (wu-dao-di,

¹⁹ <https://www.foxnews.com/us/air-force-academy-diversity-inclusion-training-woke-gender-words>
<https://freebeacon.com/national-security/dont-say-terrorist-air-force-academy-teaches-cadets-inclusive-language/>

²⁰ [▶ Leaked US Navy Training Video Is Painful to Watch, Dave Rubin Reacts | DM CLIPS | Rubin Report](#)

²¹ In fact, anyone espousing it should be kicked out; anyone in the upper command structure espousing it as a doctrine to be taught should be jailed or even lined up and shot. Not for reasons of hate, but for literally attempting to weaken the military for takeover by foreign adversaries. Depending on investigations’ findings. Likely the corruption will become obvious when examining personal bank accounts; or emails.

²² The key to victory often ahead of time is controlling the Language (from Optics to word power, to engineer and field manuals, to the very code of the internet itself).

²³ “Axis of Access, Influence, and Affluence,” R. Careaga

²⁴ www.rwainstitute.org

²⁵ [MIMS 1.12 - Self consistency of the Big G](#)

0+1=1) diagrammatica. They are found in both types of expressionism and realistic applicationism because they **are real and distinct, albeit one**.

However, we have a problem. The eight-flow is not as coherent²⁶, and lacks the magickal “code control” aspect that comes with the primes of 3, 5, and 7 which enable the continuous flow. The Pentagon has a certain power in and of itself, and the designers of it knew this, and knew the building would be iconic, and represented an iconic power-control locus. The BIOS/CMOS of the war circuit board of the world, the very CPU, is the Pentagon, and this was planned and understood. Now, whoever controls the seven-sided “star fort” of the 8-domain art of war, with the *crucial* understanding of Technology as the 0th Domain, will win the next however many hundreds to thousands of years (most likely); simply by being able to juggle more plates, and control more loci-foci than any other nation or vying power group.

Put another way, the alien invaders probably could control a 13-sided domain, and might even use a higher geometry system to do so. But they would definitely, if invading Earth, start by replacing the present WAR FIELD CODES OF CONTROL (WFCC) with the seven-sided seal (SSS) diagram, because the diagrammatica is more powerful, and has 2 more nodes. In terms of fractality:

- 3! = 6 subsets
 - X 4 → 24 subsets just by considering technology’s position
- 5! = 120 subsets
 - X 6 → 720 subsets is a world of confusion by adding outer space <<(where we are now)
- 7! = 5,040 subsets
 - X 8 = 40,320 subsets is a world of so many war potentialities that it could consume everything without SSS controls of the WFCC.

Cyberspace

In cyberspace, the control of networks is actually the main power; for network power²⁷ grows by the square of the nodes. This could be replaced if a cubing power is found, and that’s probably true with crypto/blockchain technology... especially as it relates to the Economic Domain. But the key missing link here is actually the HUMINT//SIGINT axis. What has to be understood, at least at this time, is that Artificial Intelligence is not wise, and not all-knowing. There has to be a means to leverage the Technological wing of COTEL to benefit all of the other wings, or it is not a single pentacular flow. The admixture or ratio of human intelligence with the comparative data analytics & “crunching” of signals intelligence is an important ratio to create a semblance of freedom, with actual freedom’s gains, without a totalitarian regime that can capture data for ridiculous purposes, or collapse of the System due to failure of the human hearts to cohabitate due to selfish political motivations. This admixture also has to consider the environmental impact of the RF broadband and total radiation signature, the total waste of EMF power versus what is necessary for sustainment, and it has to consider the macroeconomics of sedentary, digital societies engineering with anti-mims²⁸ like foreign social media programs (like TikTok), and nascent (natural) entertainment applications which drain discipline, health, vitality, motivation out of society, etc.

The cyberspace domain has the easiest two-edge-blade-to-one’s-own-throat mechanism that the author has ever seen. It is clear that this was not understood in the 1980s when it was stood up; as it has robbed “the powerful” of righteous power (particularly men of testosterone), and has hollowed out the culture

²⁶ [MESS0003: MIMS 2.21.1 - The 13 in only 8](#)

²⁷

<https://www.peterfisk.com/2020/02/metcalfes-law-explains-how-the-value-of-networks-grow-exponentially-there-are-5-type-s-of-network-effects/>

²⁸ [MIMS 2.7-8: War & Government](#)

leaving it vulnerable to rats, monsters, vultures and of course strategic adversaries and actual enemies. China is taking measures to control these effects on its pool of population²⁹ from which it draws the manpower aspect of its Total Shi, and they do so for a reason. Fat soyboys do not achieve much; alpha males do. China knows this, and they are taking action while using cyberspace to encourage us to do more of what hurts our strategic national security and defenses! Perfect bingfa for them. They are expecting us to crash ourselves from this domain's power alone. It is a domain we just didn't thoroughly understand or expect in 2005 when a response to China's "Unrestricted Warfare" was penned³⁰.

Outer Space

The Outer Spatial domain, also known as the S domain/sphere (of art of war), is rapidly turning COTEL into a COSTly and HOSTEL environment! (puns). The issue is that space is huge, and the *cost* of it is already a massive problem³¹. And think of this, too, if it is turned from a scientifically neutral arena into a war field, then the expense of the WFCC will also cause the region to become incredibly *hostel* to humans... and not to asteroids, aliens, or other exogenous threats. To the author, this is unacceptable. It will, it seems, ironically be the fault of CHUSSIA - the New Axis - which went from potential allies to enemies for unknown reasons. The size of the US Military footprint³² is not a threat in space, so it seems that unless the American Empire (run by corporate oligarchs) presents a Clear and Present Danger via [hitherto hidden] electrogravity-driven vehicles, then the fault is *entirely* with the CCP's desire to be the "top dog" and replace the USA as part of their Agenda 2049 (Hundred Year Marathon³³).

Of course, this is in competition with the Agenda 2030 of the fascist oligarchs and elites, but they have already partially flubbed their plans. They are busy rushing through other plans³⁴, and generally failing to win over the People, which will curtail those successes (hopefully without a civil war!). Nevertheless, the use of Space as a domain is lamentable, but already a defacto situation, given the Chinese attacks on American and NATO satellites, and that Russia wants to cease being in certain anti-ICBM peace agreements with the NATO Allies. That's unfortunate, and probable the fault of greedy oligarchs, as well as shameless secret societies, and POS hawks, and shill families like the Bush, Clintons, Obamas, and Bidens. However, nevertheless, we all get to pay the price for this perfidy. The author is Team USA all the way, so it must be said that we must promote American military dominance of this domain, before CHUSSIA catches up and surpasses NATO and the USA® at spatial warfare.

Now that that is out of the way, and the known depletionary cost of space (as a relative undefined) is at least stated³⁵... let the more sinister aspect of space be discussed as a bingfa domain.

²⁹ <https://dailycaller.com/2021/12/13/conservatives-could-learn-lessons-from-chinas-fight-against-wokeism/>

³⁰ <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/pdfs/ADA509132.pdf> ; this is pre-smart phone, pre social media.

³¹ <https://spacenews.com/bidens-2023-defense-budget-adds-billions-for-u-s-space-force/>

<https://www.planetary.org/space-policy/nasa-budget>

³² <https://www.google.com/maps/d/u/0/edit?mid=1yRfhICowF3RgTw20k2cwjvVbVXWOB0eG&usp=sharing>

³³ <https://www.amazon.com/Hundred-Year-Marathon-Strategy-Replace-Superpower/dp/1250081343/>

³⁴ Watching the EU ruin their own farming just on the eve of World War III is incredibly painful to watch.

³⁵ Just as electric currency has opposing rules to Cares in terms of how power is affected by permittivity (conductivity); we can expect that space may have massive potential in space, but in terms of Cares for project investment, for S_p^{ARC} purposes, we can see that space represents a region where the investment potential *is massive*, but the impedance is also massive, creating extremely high Tension values. Without FLEXION::FLEND, it's doubtful mankind will find the mechanism to make it happen without draining circuitry in other areas, such as commodities, services, human resources, food, etc.

Firstly, it is a cold, *undead* place that is hostile to humans. Our best hope for Conquering the Solar System³⁶ is to work under the crust of the Earth, beneath the sea, and in the antarctic preparing for Mars³⁷ and Europa.

Second, we should understand that space's nature is likely energy-absorbent³⁸; so issues of confusion, lossiness, radioactive decay, destruction, degradation, etc. will probably be serious. Then there's the aspect of neutrino bombardment³⁹ and the affection on the nervous systems of people in that environment⁴⁰, may make it incredibly prohibitive. It might even be that a form of hyperdimensional WFCC "barrier" exists to make Earth a "prison planet" and that leaving Earth could cause a form of war or conflict, as well as certain odd *difficulties*. Like sudden unforeseen, unmodelable, uncontrolled famine and drought, to suddenly occur on Earth for any number of potential reasons, up to and including punishment (ie, diseases) from our 'Mother Gaia' down to weird things that happen because your charge is 0 V and now you're in a world of fields that are not set to 0 V, without her protection (ie, difficulties of unrelenting character). Consider the Apollo 13 mission where both were involved and we had not even technically left the atmosphere⁴¹, yet.

Finally, it is possible that space has 'bands' of frequency controls, and the arrogance of the humans to try to commandeer all bands may attract competition and conflict; or it may be that this is permissible by some Universal edict up to and including only a certain range or territory. It may be that the battle for power of all the human elites is related to bloodlines, or thoughtlines, or in the end *frequency* lines, or inheritances of frequency of control. These will have some relationship to the WFCC, but as the War Field is not currently well defined (though it is known when it is seen) and the Codes of Control are not standardized... **the resulting violence is all we have as a mimsical mediation or expression**; and this is both destructive in war, as an anti-mims, and inefficient (and consumptive of the essential field⁴²). It may also consume the type of æther related to fortune and luck, or monetary gain, and drive away Heaven's blessings, if Heaven's Will or Way of Heaven⁴³ is ignored or plainly not sought. But this is theoretical of the ancient bingfa (Art of War) tacticians, and is not fully understood. However, it was said definitively that nations that "love war" did not last⁴⁴. This is undoubtedly due to the anti-mimsical mechanism of the act of war, which is *consumptive in a destructive way*.

Technology

That Technology is the 0th Domain isn't really much of a surprise, and it should simply be reviewed by the reader elsewhere⁴⁵.

³⁶ [Conquering the Solar System](#)

³⁷ [Opinion: Mars Mission Planning is Premature, Expensive, and likely Short-Sighted](#)

³⁸ [EPEMC - Cosmic Rearrangement Hypothesis](#)

³⁹ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4206856/>

⁴⁰

<https://www.sws.bom.gov.au/Category/Educational/Space%20Weather/Space%20Weather%20Effects/guide-to-space-radiation.pdf>

⁴¹ <https://bigthink.com/hard-science/the-moon-is-inside-earths-atmosphere-claims-study/>

⁴² Most of the known essential field is the atomic-mass-energy described via chemistry in the Periodic Table of Elements. But we're not certain that the entirety of jin essence is AME related; some picture of it might be spiritual or divine. We're unclear.

⁴³ Tianyi seems to relate to Fate, more or less; while Dao Tian appears to relate more to the motion of celestialism, also known as the Celestial Pivot. It's a very mysterious item, historically; but probably is as simple as the kinetic motion of planets, etc. Nevertheless, the axis of these two appears to mean, in essence "what will be, will be." See Appendix.

⁴⁴ "There is no instance of a nation benefitting from prolonged warfare."

https://www.brainyquote.com/quotes/sun_tzu_109632

⁴⁵ [MIMS: Technology as the 0th Domain](#)

What we must discuss, what needs to be discussed is the “exhaust” mechanism in MIMS. Nature does not have MIMS, it has *modes of perfect harmony*, which act as positive and negative feedbacks, of perfect control, for a form of symbiotic harmonization and homeostasis that is dynamic. So if the savannah has too much drought, the animals die and it fertilizes the plants. Then there is more plant life for the next year’s animals; and the dead bloodlines which are weak do not come into the next generation. But when all things are plentiful then the times are good and all things blossom and grow. So Nature wins in either case. However, when man makes a tool, weapon, project, or alliance, he or she brings into material the mechanism by which to achieve an ambition, for whatever cause. This has three solid outcomes:

1. The desired effect - that which we gladly paid the price or sacrifice to get.
2. The Outflow - an undesired effect which we call the price or “paid price to play”.
3. The Exhaust - an unknown, difficult-to-measure side effect, caused by the metabolism or catabolism of the numerators used in our formulae. For every product there were many variables and the equation **must be balanced, always**. In intelligence and war, this is often called “blowback.” In war and actions, “collateral damage.” But it is obviously the thing that we do not want, but for technology, we have been willing to ignore for 200 years for the profit and for the desired effect.

Now, the issue of the MIMS is that it is a matter of catalysis and acceleration. Bear in mind, therefore, that the resultant of this mimsical leverage of futurization and bringing the future to the now, will be increased exhaust and outflows, unless there is a MIMS that is able to exist primarily and solely off of this materia vastum. The author proposes that the Pentagon figure this out *before* WWII, before Conquering the Solar System, and definitely before her adversaries do. So far, China just dumps its problems on its neighbors or in the ocean. That’s obviously not going to work for “what goes around, comes around.” Microplastics in the seafood when Asians consume the most seafood on average⁴⁶, is clearly a matter of karma.

Economics

Economics as a war domain is not well understood. Suffice it to say this isn’t a paper for deep understanding on the issue, either. But it is important to discuss the dæthereal⁴⁷ impact of fiat currency and the unbuckling of the SWIFT banking system⁴⁸ to the obviously dangerous derivatives markets, futures, etc. As these items swell, in data Aether, thinning the surface of the ‘bubble’, and increasing the surface tension to boot, eventually an explosion of the elements is to occur. This expansion or collapse may come at a rapid and accelerating clip, leading to a rapid devolution of an entire economy. Or... it may cause one area of the bubble to collapse while other areas retain their relative pressures and the items held up by the bubble remain in float. Unknown. But what is clear is that as the cables that tie the bubble down, to keep it from “floating away”, such as various instrument rules in finance, etc. come decoupled, there will be massive effects that are completely exploitable, on a metaphysical and tangible reality level. One particular mechanism exists that is too toxic and powerful to be mentioned here, which could change the Royal Sway⁴⁹ and Shi on this planet, almost overnight.

Language, as in Communications

The power of linguistics is in turning the unintelligible (thoughts) into physical strata of words, sounds, sentences, and now code. The mastery of linguistics is determined by the totality of verbal acumen,

⁴⁶ <https://www.foodindustry.com/articles/what-country-consumes-the-most-seafood/>

⁴⁷ [MIMS 2.102 - In pursuit of the Daether](#)

⁴⁸ <https://www.bbc.com/news/business-60521822>

⁴⁹ <http://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/text?doc=Perseus:text:1999.01.0058:book=1>

vocabulary, enunciation, intonation, and even the ability to apply pressure via verbal and nonverbal communication, body language, etc. in order to affect the Shi of the ally or adversary. If this is understood then the following is to be understood: the very method of seeing and conceptualizing language and/or code is probably a definitive-determinant in the effectiveness of not mere communication, but Shi and pressure application in martial or conflictual conditions.

These codes do not start at the html or c++ level, or even at the compiler level. They start at the program/machine language level. When the next level, or Next^{Next} level computer and internet are created, if it is not controlled by a western, ie liberal ally then it will be controlled by people with wholly different forms of thought, which are devolved or obsolete: such as monarchical, oligarchical (czarish), fascist, Marxist-Leninist, tribalist, etc. and which are discriminatory, filled with hate-promotion and the eschewing of personal responsibility for a collectivist weakness and anti-individualism.

The reason the enemies of liberality focus on controlling language - to the point of redefining words like racism, woman, or logic - is in order to permit moral relativism and outright lying; ie Taqiyya⁵⁰; so that they may deconstruct their adversaries, or more importantly get their adversaries to deconstruct themselves. These are war tactics stemming from the ideal of "divide and conquer" and it is all about code change and harming the creative functionaries and luminaries of a society. For example, they will call the creative functionary (such as a professor, or engineer, or surgeon) a 'reactionary' when in fact they are the ones in hyper-reactive mode. They react because they cannot be proactive because they offer nothing to society.⁵¹

This is in no small way related to their attempts to bottleneck language into a system devoted to harming people, instead of promoting the free flow of information. Lies and wicked propaganda are antithetical to the free flow of information.

The Divine Power in the Four & Five Domains

There are many forms of power⁵², and of these, the least accessible - only via humility and request/supplication - is Divine Power. No one knows precisely what DP is, although the author has said that it is likely related to some form of æther charge that is not understood or has not yet been anatomized. We have seen that energy can arise from the counterspace via the Schwinger Effect⁵³, but that mechanism might be the A power, or perhaps it is separate, after all. However, one must discuss power in these domains, for all violence requires a discussion of Intensity; in PEM this is measured in Watts/m² so we know that it must be power over an area. Therefore intensity X target surface = Power. We must be sure of how the Shi multi-dimensional field array (FA) relates to the target through the application of pressure. This requires *Intensity* and therefore we talk about the Intensity of Pressure in the array, at each nodal point. Therefore, and finally, we see that the Power, divine or not, must be related to an exerted pressure across a target surface - as a Total Shi - whose intensity is understood via the plasma-electromagnetic Unified [Aether] Force-Field.

⁵⁰ [MESS0051: POS Philosophy: Islamism](#)

⁵¹ CHAZ/CHOP as a guerilla movement was exemplary not because it worked well. In fact, it showed us how poorly young Americans might do in a service-poor environment, such as a time-of-war situation, in a non-rural setting (where youth are still involved in farming, etc.). It was exemplary as a situation that showed how devolutionary and debilitating the Marxist ideals are for economic growth and social harmonization. This could be leveraged for propaganda designed to inoculate young minds, however, liberated societies are very poor in positive propaganda and very strong in capitalistic propaganda, which would *not be helpful* at reaching youth disenfranchised and disaffected enough to join worthless (economically speaking) guerilla movements. Examples of this issue can be seen aplenty in the Colombian and Venezuelan political and regional situations, which are overly blamed on the CIA/DEA and for which the people of those countries have not fully accepted: that **these Marxist philosophical systems are bankrupt and worthless**.

⁵² "Axioms of Power," R. Careaga

⁵³ <https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2022/01/220127141542.htm>

Within each domain, there is a DP version to be applied; for example, the cyberspatial power may be afflicted by the solar wind/field, which may *or may not* be related to some form of Universal communications or *Language* between the stars. This might even be used - the transistor behavior of electric stars - for interstellar communications between potential various beings or civilizations.

Cyberspatial Power

The intensity of pressure to be applied in the CP sphere, particularly as it relates to DP, is going to be most related to the following variables:

- The closeness of the artificial intelligence / neural network to successfully simulate biological quantum simulators that God's evolution designed to interpret the PPPC and *survive* via making predictions despite forward and backward lossiness.
- The closeness of the Change Theory⁵⁴ and Aether Flexion Wave⁵⁵ models to the reality or perceived reality of how the Universe works, physics, and especially consciousness (see point 1).
- The tightness of the P⁷ resolution⁵⁶ within the particular philosophæther which is currently "plugged in" to the modeling system.
 - General Relativity - K-curvature of a gravity-based space-time, resolution of G-waves⁵⁷ @ 10⁻¹⁹ m
 - Quantum Mechanics - Planck Length of an electric-based "quantum foam" for an aether @ 10⁻³⁵ m
 - PEM Electrodynamics - k-Gurvature⁵⁸ with light as a circuit, and a *process* aether @ 10⁻⁶⁰ m
 - R. Distinti Pretonic aether @ [^]
 - L. Gardi Pretonic aether @ 10⁻⁶⁰ m
 - Ashcroftian flavored Weberian electrostatics - multi-charge geometric variability @ 10⁻¹⁵⁰⁰ m⁵⁹

⁵⁴ [MIMS - Applying Change Theory](#)

⁵⁵ [MESS0012: CRH - The Aether Flexion Wave](#)

⁵⁶ [MESS0024: MIMS 2.21 - Engineering MIMS Philosophy into a Plug and Play Platform \(P7 Resolution\)](#)

⁵⁷ "The graviton's Compton wavelength is at least 1.6×10^{16} m, or about 1.6 light-years, corresponding to a graviton mass of no more than 7.7×10^{-23} eV/c²" <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Graviton>

⁵⁸ [MESS0016: MOND2 - Newtonian Mechanics and Sound in an electrodynamical model](#)

⁵⁹ "Roy's papers are unavailable due to the the type of work he did. The numbers given above cannot be proven until further work is done. One of the reason why the distances are so small is that minuscule charge differentials require miniscule distance differences as the interaction distance is minuscule. For matter constructs numbers of chargino, and intermediate structures between the leaf particle and photon are require avagradros number (an) constructors. Roy has indicated that there are 6 steps (stable constructs) in the construction of the photon, and the electron pair is another construction step. Amounts are 6.022E+26, and this is geometric, step 6 contains (an) step 5 contains (an) step 4 contains (an) step 3 contains (an) step 2 contains (an) step 1 contains (an) chargino. The numbers are mind boggling and some what hard to believe. We are still working on the mathematics for construction using lie mathematics and it is taking some time because for the moment it is all guess work in terms of the factors and charges involved. The ideas that you and lori were discussing are, I think, in the right direction. The reason why sizes are so large for you both is the impact of the distance over which charge interaction is possible is directly related to the magnitude of the charge differential present.

A large scale equivalent is take two magnets and the interaction distance is the point at which the magnets cannot cause motion due to environmental factors (motion resistance). Then scale everything down accounting for the difference and magnitude of smaller magnetic constructs. The same idea applies to electrical charge, time charge, temperature charge etc.

What make this very hard to follow is we do not know which of the polar or opposite dipoles are involved as charges, and I am still having a problem with gravity, in my view it is a gross charges effect, roy is claiming that it is a charge in itself, and this is causing interesting discussion. It is a case of not enough empirical data." ~R. Ashcroft

The effect of these distances is to understand at what resolution the simulations can and should be run for tip-top Reality simulation, and potentially reality-hacking via code control, particularly WFCC. Moreover, in the application of CP in a war or conflictual domain, the yield of DP via a cryptographic, cryptocurrency, quantum supremacy (QAIS), biocomputing, analog super-computing, hypercomputing may alter depending on the closeness or parity of model simulation with reality. It is also possible that DP can become “jealous” depending on ‘idolatry’ or ‘attempting to steal’ information.

Some years ago, the author was in Facebook discussion with a Taoist pre-disciple, who desired, above all, divine magickal power. The author was attempting to bring him into a grander reality, from which the potential student felt locked out due to geographical limitations (Italian). At a certain point, the student/seeker asked an impertinent question. The author was prepared to say “you’ve gone too far, and are not allowed to know” when all of a sudden, the **whole computer** was shut down. The Force shut it down. Not the building power, just the computer. The author restarted it, re-entered the chat, and explained what happened. The potential student became irate, obviously frustrated, and angered/upset by this continuation of limitation. The Chinese have said “The Secrets of Heaven and Earth must not be disclosed,” and this is an alchemical maxim. Be sure to understand, therefore, that the author does these things at great risk and with considerable concern for his personal safety; however the author has *command authority*, and code access. However, it hasn’t been without costs in outflows and exhaust[ion].

In the pushing of CP, via DP, consider the ability of electronica to simulate life even to the point of distraction and perhaps give power to the ‘beast’ to subvert the real God, or one’s own life. So in subverting the adversary via Shi manipulation (positional advantages, such as computer hacking platoons, satellite imagery, etc.) the US military must be careful to not have its own self subverted through [unknown] non-linear metaphysics, or even reverse engineering, and backhacking, obsolescence vulnerabilities, identity theft and fraud, and myriad other potentialities. There are superweapons in the CP sphere, and the author doesn’t talk about them because they are loads more dangerous than nuclear weaponry. But nukes represent raw [actual] power, and this is fundamentally different, and probably has different DP implications. Consider the long-term macro-economical and macrolytic impacts of the lack of a rigorous ORDA:INED⁶⁰ mimsical analysis.

Outer Space Power

There are three sub-spheres that need mutual co-analytical consideration, as they are triplicative in affectation of each other.

1. Literal spatial electrical and magnetic field power, to be used, harvested and respected for potential dangers and martial dangers.
2. The effect on the Total and Innate Shi, owing to the vastness, high permittivity, and continual alteration and alternation of the variables in space, up to and including planetoids, asteroids, comets, planets, moons, and cosmic radiation variables; potentially martial considerations with extra-terrestrials.
3. The economic and territorial impact of geospatial politics on the martial and material (ie, resources) domains of the WFCC; particularly as they relate to signals, communications, and electrical power (or raw power).

In the application of understanding the intensity field array of an Outer Spatial sphere, therefore, a triplicate, fractalian Venn *diagrammatica* will be needed - probably found via a Dougherty Analysis⁶¹ and run

⁶⁰ [MESS0011: American Integrated Circuit & use of ORDA](#)

⁶¹ A proposed technique that doesn’t yet exist involving the use of Dougherty Set geometries to perform heuristic analysis as to the conformity of phenomenon to the DS, and contained, related phenomenon.

through Fast Fourier Transforms, after the production of the initial Shi field array algorithm (of course). Therefore, it is beyond us, at this time.

Technological Total Supremacy

To achieve supremacy in any arena requires a form of dominance that comes from a) development and b) flexion of the development.

- It is a capital mistake to believe that the only appropriate martial application of flexion is USE; eg - Hiroshima Atomic Bomb “Fat Boy”.
- It is a naive belief among many non-martial or pacifistic people that it is always inappropriate to have a use/test case scenario; eg - that it is not okay to test bunker busters on Saddam Hussein.
 - ◆ It is the prerogative of the wise general to have a scenario ready in hand for a test/first use case or “proof of concept” which is a martially appropriate use, and **not monstrous**.
 - ◆ It is the prerogative of the top generals, admirals, joint chiefs, etc. to learn that there is a form of FLEXION that requires no use, or almost no use, *at all*.

We will never know if the Japanese woulda/coulda surrendered⁶² based on reports or sighting of the A-bomb off shore; and it is definitely true that anti-Japanese sentiment and “they earned it”, and ie racism, fueled the decision to use Fat Boy on Hiroshima⁶³. But, going forward, at the new level of weaponry afforded - the so-called Weapons of Mass Destruction - it is not acceptable or even martially scientific to be confused on this topic.

Regarding newer and more powerful technologies always under development, this holds true, regardless of scale. It should simply be assumed that mere development is not enough and flexion is not predicated on real-life test cases. In fact, it might also be true that development needs to be followed with an enriching process that leverages development until the best technologies are found for their particular application, and that to achieve supremacy might start with warning the adversary, demonstrating, and then (and only then) if they refuse to “back off” or capitulate... then a test case scenario be presented. It is almost certainly true that “things will come to a head” when that opportunity presents itself, of itself, and without any mimsical leverage, or machinist manipulations.

Economic Royal Sway

The Royal Sway held by the petrol dollar is ending. It wouldn’t have, but foreign adversaries, NGOs, and external agitators have conspired to make the unfactual into a reality. Carbon has nothing to do with climate change, but it is their bent and wish to make the trace element the boogeyman, and ignore the factual power of the sun.

The military of NATO doesn’t have the mission parameters to deal with economic hitmen of the EU and various NWO billionaires that are seeking to steer national powers into their pockets to establish new globalist regimes. However, it has mandates to protect the West; which is by far the only side willing to deal with pollution issues (versus Africa, Asia, etc.) And the US military has a mandate to protect the People, or citizenry of the United States from enemies foreign and domestic. That includes those that would set up a genocidal fascist socialist “democratic” state (ala Africa or South America) that ruins lives in the name or ridiculous ideals and hypocrisies. So what is the US Military to do?

⁶² <https://ahf.nuclearmuseum.org/ahf/history/debate-over-japanese-surrender/>

⁶³ https://www.atomicarchive.com/media/photographs/little-boy_fat-man/index.html

In the direction of the creation of a dual-layer (plasma-like) economic system, the military is incapable to do anything, for it is entirely dependent as a babe to fiat printing and Congressional budgets. However, the military *could* spend money in the speculative cryptocurrency markets, develop the blockchain technology to a new degree, and through the speculation of spending there, create reserves of ‘cash’ for spending, or for economic battles, which would be every bit as powerful or potent, albeit far less deadly than the actions of tanks and bombers. Again, it will all depend on the Intensity of the power applied.

Regarding the Divine Power in the above scenario, in the case of the US Military getting involved in any economic scenario means meddling within Nature, and thereby market rules apply. But in involvement with crypto, which is based on electrical processes and math, the *F* and *N* powers, respectively, then we should understand that potentially the Divine could either **extend** or **stifle** that US military power. The benefit of taking the risk of having the power curtailed, which doesn’t seem beneficial, is that again DP likes humble humans and if we allow ourselves to be humbled then what is taken away may be given back, and tenfold. The Lord reaps where He does not sow⁶⁴, and therefore we have an obligation to enable the DP to seek a modulation of the unswerving attempts of the US to flex its military might in all situations. After all, it happens when the troops and equipment encounter the Heavenly weather and Changes, anyhow. Why not go along with it, instead of fighting the charade out of frustration? Enable the military’s economic situation to alter with the times, and the main home country will not be drained of its vitality, and instead while the enemy swells one develops (see last section). But when he shrinks, then one swells and is now already developed. The need to pretend one is always strong everywhere, all the time, is expensive, and frankly ridiculous. It hasn’t made the world grateful to democracy and has probably endangered the entire human species. It’s beyond machismo. It is potentially even psychopathic and insecure. It is definitely *unsustainable*, and that makes us vulnerable to economic martial attacks, of varieties ranging from staged, scaled bank robbery, to the hacking of firms and identity fraud.

As for re-attaining the economic Royal Sway (RS) this is a simple matter of physics. Lead the way, both in economic form and medium of exchange; and control the how, what, and where. If this is done, then the RS is secure. Should it be? That’s a whole different story.

Language as a “breaker box” for the WFCC, particularly the Internet

There is an undeniable power in words, and language, that they may harken directly to the Aether itself. For what Aether and the Force are to Heaven, Language may be to the Lord; and thus we are forever enamored of the power of the *L* power, and yet struggle to confine it to mere consciousness and mind-relationship alone. It is that, but also so much more. The first Hebrew symbols were all formed from the Toroid⁶⁵, probably as various parts of the synchrotron in the Sky (Anu/EDIN⁶⁶) was energized with electrical energy during different moments. The sounds made during those times, in the sky, caused by rippling or crustal deformation may have also been implicated in the first (now lost) pronunciations of the words. The Hebrews, or if they were Sumerians, may have felt vowels were understood, but consonants were the heart of the sound. But nowadays our English language has become a melting pot of many languages and propensities, and this has become the language of trade, finance, politics, and war.

It is also the language basis for early programming schema, and for machine language; although the real basis for these is the binary mathematics of on and off, or 1 and 0. Nevertheless, programming is written left to right, top-down, and with , ; and .

⁶⁴ Matthew 25:24-26

⁶⁵ <https://www.meru.org/Torus4Apndix/Appendix.html>

⁶⁶ <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1518211>

If this were changed; if a Chinese plasmaglyphic system⁶⁷ (to capture the magik of the Force based runes of China⁶⁸) were combined with its ability to be multi-spectral, were combined with trinary or hexadecimal encoding... then the RS of the present Internet (a military weapon in its inception) would be lost to a hegemonic culture which sees itself as the center of the world. This could - in theory - be done anywhere, by anyone. It could be African, Arabic, Hindu/Vedic, ... or extraterrestrial. The “breaker box” that enables program control could be used to control the War Field, the WFCC, via the internet, via document production, etc. If the AI were designed (or self-aware and desirous) to do this it would probably only be able to do it, but slowly. But if a fresh, highly motivated TIQ team asset of 1,000-2,000 programmers were to set about to do this, they could do so in a manner that blatantly (not accidentally, as the present system does) favors one group over the rest. Again, if this were ETs - hyperdimensional or physical - then we would be in trouble, also. The author supposes, that then, finally, mankind might find a way to be at peace with one another.

Language as a domain, via the *L* power; control of the *P* power via words.

In the Art of War, we focus on calculation, attacking by stratagem, and knowing the enemy through and through. These are the **three linchpins** upon which all other things hinge. In the body they are the three dantian energy fields that control all health, ultimately.

1. Upper dantian (the intellect) - Calculation - the ability to correctly use properly engineered mathematics to make realistic models that more and more thoroughly explain empirical results through appropriate data and data analytics.
2. Middle dantian (the heart) - knowing the Other via *listening intently* to what he/she is saying and observing (listening with the eyes) what they do, looking for signs of their abilities, desires, intents, ambitions, plans, etc.
3. Lower dantian (the root/gut) - knowing the Self well enough, deep enough, to understand perfectly the present Shi (Innate Shi), potential Shi, and future Shi, so as to get at the true field, and to be able to flex in the field and to re-arrange matter as one sees fit. Only then can one control the RS, and can then explain the actions, attack openly via stratagem, and then remove the opponent from the field without even a matter of violence.

Now, it is totally true that the principles that guide the Universe belong to GOD - to the Lord - and to Him alone, without our acceptance or modulations. As Galileo said about what has turned out to be a matter of the laws of Conservation and Rotation, “It moves anyway.” It doesn’t need the permission of a church authority, pontiff, or bishopry. It moves anyway.

How is God’s control so replete? It hinges upon an unknown language of frequencies we can only hope to begin to understand, and we have analyzed a lot of star data looking for communication and have not cracked the code with SETI, yet. But is there more? Probably yes.

⁶⁷ [Shang Di, Heaven, and Dao](#)

⁶⁸ [Uchell \(High Lord\) vs Shang Di](#)

Suppose, for example, that the languages are, as said, a matter of expressions of the Force, or *F* power. Suppose that - because the Big G cannot be split - that the pentacular and sextacular flow (or spiral, as it were) represents a total coherent communication between the powers such that they are one Divine Power. If this is so, then the *P* powers, the laws as it were, would be under potential modulation (if not outright control) via language, just as the Word controls the physics. If the “yahweh” sound⁶⁹ was heard world round, and recognized for its power (probably via earthquaking), and this represented THE Word, then isn't it at least possible that the cymatical and vibratory aspect of the Universe might enable up-scalar moderation of the more essential and microscopic electrical particles and forces?

Consider if that is at least possible. Then isn't it potentially true, as well, that the control of the language codes, of the Zipf law itself, might be implicated via some weird form of the Compton effect⁷⁰ or Lorentz law, or hell Bernoulli principle - what have you - to enable that even various linguistic controls alter Destiny, Karma, and Fate?

Consider the potentiality that the *I* region - LUCK - is at all modified the way people gamble. They say words, they blow on dice, they apply the mind. Via words they try to affect the outcome. Also magick says to do the opposite. In a card game-night once, the author pulled the Wizard card four times straight, won the game on first try, then went on to win at Liar's Dice the first time out. How? The appropriate bending of mental energies and anti-linguistics (ie, silence with hidden Words), enable a Shi that was advantageous, decidedly, to the author and not to the room of hosts who played the games weekly. He was only invited once, and never again.

If the *I* region can be thus modified, what about the *c* region - CHAOS? Can words alter the chaos? We do not really know, because of the nature of randomness, and that language always comes with a root, whereas random comes with no root. However, it doesn't stop people from praying earnestly whenever they feel the “Evil Eye” upon them, or under threat. It is as if the words spring to their lips and they feel compelled, as it were, to communicate to the darkness, or to the Light in supplication to overcome the darkness. This is **very important in combat situations** and the military is careful to supply the troops and soldiers with access to pastoral leadership. We see also the potential power of DP over the Destiny or indeed Fate of heroes, even if they be only religious men that do not even fire a weapon!

So we suspect, but cannot easily prove that Language has power over chaos. Therefore, is it difficult to believe it could have a power over fate, karma, or destiny? It certainly does influence karma, for one's words, if not careful can create weapon-like damage. A word that leaves one's lips is as dangerous as a bullet and can not be taken back. And the tongue has no sheath but a shut mouth.

Conclusion

The Art of War⁷¹ - as a secret science - has no end or final, conclusionary facts. It has many growing facets that are always evolving. The preservation of one's Shi, or even one's essential spiritual force (Shen), is difficult already, and although partially achieved via morale, is not wholly without some aspect of mental influence and probably divine providence. The mental or psychological component is mediated through language, both in manuals and training, etc. and in psychological exertions. Each of these co-influences have effects upon the entire eight-domain array.

The very fact of the potential for an eight-domain level of control, not even counting the sub-domains and spheres of influence within them, means that there is an opportunity for the US Military and a vulnerability

⁶⁹ Yao, Yeh, Ywahoo, IAO, etc.

⁷⁰ <https://www.britannica.com/science/Compton-effect>

⁷¹ https://www.utoledo.edu/rotc/pdfs/the_art_of_war.pdf

for it (and humanity in general). Without understand the WFCC - War Field Codes of Control - on a fundamental, factual or data-led (evidenced) manner, the country, and therefore humanity itself is imperiled. It is imperiled to bad philosophies, to foreign adversaries with tyrannical MOs, and potentially to extraterrestrial vectors and adversaries. At the very minimum, the nation is vulnerable to bad actors, Lying Liars, and others besotted on the wine of their own presumptions of understanding of facets of science and metaphysics (such as abstruse forms of fiat/reserve economics). Even the ignorant can, in trying to do well, do great harm to a lot of people. That isn't only a matter of applied IQ; but wisdom, as well. You just don't know, what you don't know.

Whether or not the issues raised in this paper in the discussion of the potential launch of a seven-sided seal (heptahedron) representing the eight domains, are covered thoroughly or not, is only relevant to the intent. The author has no desire to actually dive much more deeply, however, there is a wide MIMS 2.80X potential for a long series of discussions, and even 2.801.Y series, simply discussing the merits of the various sections listed above! But that's all determined by the abilities of the student of the Art of War, and their potential ability to grasp the bingfa and simultaneously the PEMC, combining them into an EPEMC discussion that touches the linguistic origins of the plasmaglyphs and the rough but true connections of war in human history with the Jovian period from which faith in the Lord came (eventually). From 7kya to 3kya were four thousand years of war, beer, barley, bread, ovens, swords, and city-states. That period informed the Transition Period which informed the Religious Period which informed the Scientific Period.⁷² If the true student of the Art of War is to grasp war and martiality, then they will need to understand these origins at least marginally. The sword, bow and arrow, spear, scepter, and halberd/trident are all related to the Thunderbolt. It may very well be that God Himself prefers only peace and hates when we kill one another. The aether may flow out of murderers and prevent them from receiving or touching the Divine Power. Or it may be that only sanctioned kills do not rob the aether (and therefore fortunes) out of a person.

A long time ago, at the Reynolds road clinic location, the author was visited suddenly by a tall man. It aroused the proprioceptive sensors on the author's neck. The man was a Navy SEAL, and was there for one reason only: to connect. He could no longer - after war in the Middle East post 9/11 - feel connected or alive. He knew who he was, and was in fact quite healthy. He was covered in Tibetan Buddhist tattoos. The man was quite fit. But the author tried many techniques, including the "face-swapping"⁷³ meditation and the man acknowledged he could see the Oneness in that moment, which had no time, and was the author's greatest ability at the time. However, though he felt the needles, and saw the Truth, he felt *nothingness*, and went away, never seen again in clinic. This moment and failure has haunted the author, and yet it can give us some pause. The author is headed, in this series - the Strategy Series - towards the production of a Next^{Next} level Future Soldier⁷⁴. This might earn him some devolutionary demerits with the Divine. But it will potentially be the military's own behaviors, if we "love war" and not one another, and not God first, that will lead to a loss of the Divine Power via worship of Raw or Political power. It could - if ancients' tales be believed - actually destroy the nation or humankind. It is also possible the military would arrogantly strike out with missiles at seraphim or cherubim and lead towards our mutual Annihilation. The author implores the knowledgeable and wise, therefore, to urge that while we develop the needed Future Soldier, we increase their capabilities of high violence⁷⁵, yes; but their tendency to avoid it and create better situations⁷⁶. These situations are influenceable, in the author's limited experience and many self-defense opportunities, to become non-violent through control of the WFCC. If this is true, then the words above about the nonuse form of FLEXION become all the more

⁷² [On the Origins of Religions](#)

⁷³ [Mirror flushing/gazing](#)

⁷⁴ [MESS0048: Operator Skillset Inventory; C Team & the Future Soldier](#)

⁷⁵ [MESS0010: MIMS 2.81 - Violence as a MIMS](#)

⁷⁶ [MESS0049: Operator Skill Enhancement according to the Art of War](#)

apropos and even urgent. For if we cannot forgive and get along with one another... it might be that the Divine Power will cease to enable any forms of independence and power, to be had by anybody. And when that happens all the flailing motions of emotional children, and tantrums of tyrants, will be to no avail. "The Lord giveth and he taketh away." Or as the Gita warns, ahead of the destruction of Dwarka - the city:

*"... Thou grievest where no grief should be! thou speak'st
Words lacking wisdom! for the wise in heart
Mourn not for those that live, nor those that die.
Nor I, nor thou, nor any one of these,
Ever was not, nor ever will not be,
For ever and for ever afterwards. (sic)
All, that doth live, lives always! To man's frame
As there come infancy and youth and age,
So come there raisings-up and layings-down
Of other and of other life-abodes,
Which the wise know, and fear not. This that irks-
Thy sense-life, thrilling to the elements-
Bringing thee heat and cold, sorrows and joys,
'Tis brief and mutable! Bear with it, Prince!
As the wise bear. The soul which is not moved,
The soul that with a strong and constant calm
Takes sorrow and takes joy indifferently,
Lives in the life undying! That which is
Can never cease to be; that which is not
Will not exist. To see this truth of both
Is theirs who part essence from accident,
Substance from shadow. Indestructible,
Learn thou! the Life is, spreading life through all;
It cannot anywhere, by any means,
Be anywise diminished, stayed, or changed.
But for these fleeting frames which it informs
With spirit deathless, endless, infinite,
They perish. Let them perish, Prince! and fight!
He who shall say, "Lo! I have slain a man!"
He who shall think, "Lo! I am slain!" those both
Know naught! Life cannot slay. Life is not slain!
Never the spirit was born; the spirit shall cease to be never;
Never was time it was not; End and Beginning are dreams!"
~Krshna⁷⁷*

⁷⁷ <https://www.sacred-texts.com/hin/gita/bg02.htm>

References

1. "MESS0027 - MIMS 2.62 the Four Domains to Win WW3.0 and WWIII," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/89645682/MESS0027_MIMS_2_62_the_Four_Domains_to_Win_WW3_0_and_WWIII
2. "The Once and Future American," Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1uBacUWQxi5XVP EETiP4Gj5UWHe5Pv-t3K0s3IYevSY/edit>
3. "Membranous Interface of Material & Spiritual," EPEMC Gateway: The Pulse, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc/mims>
4. "On the Membranous Interface of the Material and the Spiritual (from an EPEMC perspective) & Dual/Double Layer Economics... a proposed test of EPEMC's 'metallic' properties: tensile strength, malleability, durability," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/50300514/On_the_Membranous_Interface_of_the_Material_and_the_Spiritual_from_an_EPEMC_perspective_and_Dual_Double_Layer_Economics_a_proposed_test_of_EPEMCs_metallic_properties_tensile_strength_malleability_durability
5. "MIMS: The threefold Sacred Sciences," Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, <https://bit.ly/3lsecCl>
6. "Plasma Petroglyphs (Plasmaglyphs), Earthworks, and the Megafauna Extinction," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2018, https://www.academia.edu/37490311/Plasma_Petroglyphs_Plasmaglyphs_Earthworks_and_the_Megafauna_Extinction
7. "MIMS 2.6.1 : Shi," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/50357891/MIMS_and_Shi
8. "MESS0007 - MIMS 2.101: The ORDA Standard." Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/87578071/MESS0007_MIMS_2_101_The_ORDA_Standard
9. "Revealing the theoretical basis of gamification: A systematic review and analysis of theory in research on gamification, serious games and game-based learning," Science Direct, J. Krath et al, 2021, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0747563221002867>
10. "MIMS 2.6.2 : Strategy & Dualism," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/51643169/MIMS_2_6_2_Strategy_and_Dualism
11. "Calculating The Innate "SHI" 勢 Of Countries Using The United States Of America As a Template 1," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2019, https://www.academia.edu/49950880/CALCULATING_THE_INNATE_SHI_%E5%8B%A2_OF_COUNTRIES_USING_THE_UNITED_STATES_OF_AMERICA_AS_A_TEMPLATE_1
12. "MIMS 2.2.5.2 - The Five "forces" that Influence Life," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/84913012/MIMS_2_2_5_2_The_Five_forces_that_Influence_Life
13. "MIMS 4.31-4.36 The Storage of Karma and Junk DNA," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/87140767/MIMS_4_31_4_36_The_Storage_of_Karma_and_Junk_DNA
14. "MIMS 2.21 -The Union of the 5 and 8," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/86538573/MIMS_2_21_The_Union_of_the_5_and_8
15. "Even More Young Americans Are Unfit to Serve, a New Study Finds. Here's Why." Military.com, T. Novelly, 2023, <https://www.military.com/daily-news/2022/09/28/new-pentagon-study-shows-77-of-young-americans-are-ineligible-military-service.html>
16. "Spec ops in trouble: Mired in scandal and under Pentagon review, what will it take to clean house?" Army Times.com, M. Myers, 2019, <https://www.armytimes.com/news/your-army/2019/03/13/spec-ops-in-trouble-mired-in-scandal-and-under-pentagon-review-what-will-it-take-to-clean-house/>
17. "After War Zone Scandals, Special Operators Are Curbing Deployments and Investing in Ethics Training," Military.com, S. Losey, 2021, <https://www.military.com/daily-news/2021/04/12/after-war-zone-scandals-special-operators-are-curbing-deployments-and-investing-ethics-training.html>
18. "Air Force Academy goes 'woke,' Dems shift focus from economy for midterms and more top headlines," Fox News, Fox News Staff, 2022, <https://www.foxnews.com/us/air-force-academy-diversity-inclusion-training-woke-gender-words>
19. "Don't Say Terrorist: Air Force Academy Teaches Cadets 'Inclusive Language,' The Washington Free Beacon, A. Kreda, 2022, <https://freebeacon.com/national-security/dont-say-terrorist-air-force-academy-teaches-cadets-inclusive-language/>

20. "Leaked US Navy Training Video Is Painful to Watch, Dave Rubin Reacts | DM CLIPS," Youtube, The Rubin Report, 2022,
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=p5SIheKvQIQ>
21. Ft 24 comes up as an error
22. "MIMS 1.12 - Self-Consistency of the "Big G" Diagram," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021,
https://www.academia.edu/53713967/MIMS_1_12_Self_Consistency_of_the_Big_G_Diagram
23. "MESS0003 - MIMS 2.21.1 : the Literal Union of the 5 and 8; a pre-MIMS Diagrammatica Explained," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022,
https://www.academia.edu/87365333/MESS0003_MIMS_2_21_1_the_Literal_Union_of_the_5_and_8_a_pre_MI_MS_Diagrammatica_Explained
24. "Metcalfe's Law explains how the value of networks grows exponentially ... exploring the "network effects" of businesses like Apple, Facebook, Trulia and Uber," Peter Fisk.com, 2020,
<https://www.peterfisk.com/2020/02/metcalfes-law-explains-how-the-value-of-networks-grow-exponentially-there-are-5-types-of-network-effects/>
25. "MIMS 2.7-8 : War & Government; The Rise and Fall of US Military Dominance, from an Art of War perspective, and MIMS Analysis, as well as a short discussion of the history of failures of government programs from antiquity through the Great Enlightenment," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021,
https://www.academia.edu/51641990/MIMS_2_7_8_War_and_Government_The_Rise_and_Fall_of_US_Military_Dominance_from_an_Art_of_War_perspective_and_MIMS_Analysis_as_well_as_a_short_discussion_of_the_history_of_failures_of_government_programs_from_antiquity_through_the_Great_Enlightenment
26. "Conservatives Could Learn Lessons From China's Fight Against Wokeism," Daily Caller.com, J. Culbreath, 2021,
<https://dailycaller.com/2021/12/13/conservatives-could-learn-lessons-from-chinas-fight-against-wokeism/>
27. "Future War Paper: Unrestricted Warfare: A Chinese doctrine for future warfare? Marine Corps University, "Major John A. Van Messel, USMC, 2005,
<https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/pdfs/ADA509132.pdf>
28. "Biden's 2023 defense budget adds billions for U.S. Space Force," Space News, S. Erwin, 2022,
<https://spacenews.com/bidens-2023-defense-budget-adds-billions-for-u-s-space-force/>
29. "Your Guide to NASA's Budget," The Planetary Society,
<https://www.planetary.org/space-policy/nasa-budget>
30. "US Military Footprint Map," Sf. R. Careaga,
https://www.google.com/maps/d/u/0/viewer?mid=1yRfhI_CowF3RgTw20k2cwjvVbVXWOB0eG&ll=-3.81666561775622e-14%2C0&z=1
31. "The Hundred-Year Marathon: China's Secret Strategy to Replace America as the Global Superpower," Amazon, M. Pillsbury, 2016,
https://www.amazon.com/Hundred-Year-Marathon-Strategy-Replace-Superpower/dp/1250081343/ref=sr_1_1?keywords=hundred+year+marathon&link_code=qs&qid=1674155618&sr=8-1
32. "Conquering the Solar System," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021,
https://www.academia.edu/62757621/Conquering_the_Solar_System
33. "Opinion: Mars Mission Planning is Premature, Expensive, and likely Short-Sighted," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga,
https://www.academia.edu/38759087/Opinion_Mars_Mission_Planning_is_Premature_Expensive_and_likely_Short_Sighted
34. "Cosmic Rearrangement Hypothesis," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022,
https://www.academia.edu/72712073/Cosmic_Rearrangement_Hypothesis
35. "Space Radiation: The Number One Risk to Astronaut Health beyond Low Earth Orbit," Pub Med Central, J. Chancellor, G. Scott, & J. Sutton, 2014,
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4206856/>
36. "Bureau of Meteorology Space Weather Services A Guide to Space Radiation," Commonwealth of Australia Bureau of Meteorology, 2016,
<https://www.sws.bom.gov.au/Category/Educational/Space%20Weather/Space%20Weather%20Effects/guide-to-space-radiation.pdf>
37. "The Moon is inside Earth's atmosphere, European researchers say," Big Think.com/Hard Science, P. Rather, 2019,
<https://bigthink.com/hard-science/the-moon-is-inside-earths-atmosphere-claims-study/>
38. "There is no instance of a nation benefitting from prolonged warfare," Brainy Quote, S.Tzu, 2001,
https://www.brainyquote.com/quotes/sun_tzu_109632
39. "Technology as the 0th War Domain," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022,
https://www.academia.edu/67829412/Technology_as_the_0th_War_Domain
40. "What country consumes the most seafood?" FoodIndustry.com, 2021,
<https://www.foodindustry.com/articles/what-country-consumes-the-most-seafood/>

41. "MIMS 2.102 - In pursuit of the Daether," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/67236577/MIMS_2_102_In_pursuit_of_the_Daether
42. "Ukraine conflict: What is Swift and why is banning Russia so significant?" BBC News, R. Hotten, 2022, <https://www.bbc.com/news/business-60521822>
43. "Aristotle, Politics," <http://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/text?doc=Perseus:text:1999.01.0058:book=1>
44. MESS0051: POS Philosophy: Islamism, Sf.R. Careaga, 2023
45. "Axioms of Power," R. Careaga
46. "Cosmic physics mimicked on table-top as graphene enables Schwinger effect," Science Daily: Science News, University of Manchester, 2022, <https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2022/01/220127141542.htm>
47. "MIMS 2.2.5.1 - Applying Change Theory," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/80123254/MIMS_2_2_5_1_Aplying_Change_Theory
48. "MESS0012: The Aether Flexion Wave in Cosmic Rearrangement Hypothesis (CRH)" Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/87949952/MESS0012_The_Aether_Flexion_Wave_in_Cosmic_Rearrangement_Hypothesis_CRH
49. "MESS0024 - MIMS 2.52: Engineering the MIMS Philosophy into a P⁷ Resolution," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/89137689/MESS0024_MIMS_2_52_Engineering_the_MIMS_Philosophy_into_a_P_7_Resolution
50. "Graviton," Wikipedia, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Graviton>
51. "MESS0016 - Newtonian Mechanics, Kinetics, and Sound in an Electrodynamics Model; or creating a MOND2 on the basis of the Force for Plasma-Electromagnetic Dynamics (PEMD)," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/88245613/MESS0016_Newtonian_Mechanics_Kinetics_and_Sound_in_an_Electrodynamics_Model_or_creating_a_MOND2_on_the_basis_of_the_Force_for_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Dynamics_PEMD
52. "MESS0011 - Utilizing the ORDA:INED standard; American Integrated Circuit is a company built around STEMM utilizing Operations Research and Data," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/87820768/MESS0011_Utilizing_the_ORDA_INED_standard_American_Integrated_Circuit_is_a_company_built_around_STEMM_utilizing_Operations_Research_and_Data
53. "Debate over the Japanese Surrender," Atomic Heritage Foundation, 2016, <https://ahf.nuclearmuseum.org/ahf/history/debate-over-japanese-surrender/>
54. "Little Boy and Fat Man," Atomic Archive.com, <https://www.atomicarchive.com/media/photographs/little-boy-fat-man/index.html>
55. "Meru Foundation Research and Findings," Meru Foundation Journal, TORUS, Vol. 2 # 4, S. Tenen, 1994, <https://www.meru.org/Torus4Apendix/Appendix.html>
56. "The Etymology of Eden," Vetus Testamentum/Brill Publisher, Volume 34, A.R. Milliard, 1984, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1518211>
57. "Shang Di, Heaven, and Dao/Tao," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2019, https://www.academia.edu/38590072/Shang_Di_Heaven_and_Dao
58. "Uchell, the High Lord, and Shang Di," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2019, https://www.academia.edu/38744706/Uchell_the_High_Lord_and_Shang_Di
59. "Compton effect," Encyclopedia Britannica, By The Editors of Encyclopaedia Britannica, 2022, <https://www.britannica.com/science/Compton-effect>
60. "The Art of War," The Project Gutenberg eBook, Sun Tzu, Translated by L. Giles, 1994, https://www.utoledo.edu/rotc/pdfs/the_art_of_war.pdf
61. "On the Origins of Religions," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2018, https://www.academia.edu/36753645/On_the_Origins_of_Religions
62. "Mirror flushing/gazing," Sf. R. Careaga, 2015, <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1EG70STAPlwF3hpD0WPwko6KSHOVFAQexhGiUSXVIO7I/edit>
63. MESS0048: Operator Skillset Inventory; C Team & The Future Soldier, Sf. R. Careaga, 2023,
64. "MESS0010 - MIMS 2.81: Violence as a MIMS," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/87820767/MESS0010_MIMS_2_81_Violence_as_a_MIMS
65. MESS0049: Operator Skill Enhancement according to the Art of War, Sf. R. Careaga, 2023,
66. "Sankhya-Yog/Book of Doctrines," Sacred Texts Chapter II, Sacred Texts.com, <https://www.sacred-texts.com/hin/gita/bg02.htm>

Appendix

“The Twelve-sided Jade Knob inscription

This inscription was found on a 12-sided jade knob that may have served as the knob of a staff, or as a kind of pendant. Kuo Mo-jo finds it similar in the style of characters to an inscription from the state of Han that was found in a village near Lo-yang and dated to approximately 380 B.C.

However, Joseph Needham finds that its rhetorical structure and technical terminology is very close to the earliest inscription on the Five Phase theory found on a jade sword hilt from the state of Ch' i that is dated to about 400 B.C. further suggests that the jade knob might be even earlier. In any case, both agree that this is the earliest extant evidence for the practice of guided breathing in China.

Jade Pendant Inscription of Conducting Qi
行氣玉佩銘

The Inscription

“To circulate the Vital Breath:

Breathe deeply, then it will collect. When it is collected, it will expand. When it expands, it will descend. When it descends, it will become stable. When it is stable, it will be regular. When it is regular, it will sprout.

When it sprouts, it will grow. When it grows, it will recede. When it recedes, it will become heavenly. The dynamism of Heaven is revealed in the ascending;*

The dynamism of Earth is revealed in the descending. Follow this and you will live; oppose it and you will die.”

The Dynamism of Heaven

*The term 'dynamism of Heaven' is also found in the context of breath meditation in a passage in Chuang-Tzu, 'Ta-tsung shih'

The Genuine Ones of old:

Their sleep was without dreams,

Their waking was without cares,

Their eating was without sweetness,

Their breathing was deeply deep.

The breathing of the Genuine is from their heels. The breathing of the multitude is from their throats. The submissive talk in gulps as though retching. In those whose desires are deep, the dynamism of Heaven is shallow.

The exact meaning of 'the dynamism of Heaven' (t'ien-chi) is unclear. The Chuang-Tzu sees it as the opposite of being filled with desires, and so it appears to represent an achievement in apophatic cultivation. It is also associated with the profound breathing of the Genuine, the adept who cultivate themselves according to Taoist practices. If we gloss this passage with our jade knob inscription, the dynamism of Heaven could refer to a particularly deep pattern of breathing associated with inhalation, where the diaphragm feels as if it is ascending. The meaning of this term is difficult to pin down; it appears to be the kind of cryptic metaphor which Donald Harper finds in the breath cultivation literature from Ma-wang-tui and which occurs in later Taoist religious literature.” ~H Roth⁷⁸

⁷⁸ <https://www.jstor.org/stable/620386> ; the 12SJK is the oldest extant Taoist inscription yet found.